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COAL FIRE DETECTION USING THERMAL INFRARED REMOTE SENSING TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

Fires in coal mines are an environmental and economic problem of international magnitude. Basically, a mine fire is where something usually coal has caught fire underground and is steadily burning away. In other words, the term coal fire refers to burning or smoldering of coal seam, coal storage pile or coal waste pile. Thermal-infrared remote sensing exploits the fact that everything above absolute zero (-273°C) emits radiation in the thermal infrared range of the electromagnetic spectrum. These sensors record differences in the received infrared radiation from various objects. Since these differences are often considerable, an infrared image can exhibit wide range of contrasts. Further, for the sake of ground truth conventional borehole temperature measurement in coal seams is used to identify subsurface fires so as to validate the processed remote sensing data. This paper deals with, how thermal infrared remote sensing techniques can be used to predict and monitor coal fires.

Introduction

Subsurface and surface coal fires are a serious problem in many coal producing countries. Combustion can occur either within coal seam, in piles of stored coal or in spoils dumps on the surface. Apart from consuming a valuable resource, it poses enormous operational difficulties by increasing the cost of production or by making existing operations uneconomical. Noxious gases such as SO_x, NO_x and CO often affect the immediate surroundings of an active coal fire. The emission of coal fires not only pollute the local atmosphere, but also add substantial amounts of greenhouse gases. Large amount of particulate matter are also emitted into the surrounding areas and increase the aerosol loading in the local atmosphere (*Banerjee, 1985*). Another associated problem is widespread cracking and subsidence of land surface. As the burned coal turns into ash, voids are created and often the rock overburden can no longer be supported and deep cracks open up. Eventually, the surface collapses. Further, contributions of coal fires to climatic changes and global warming can't be ignored (*Collins, 2000*)

Coal fires on the surface as a high temperature event emit significant thermal energy that is easy to detect by any remote sensing scanner. Thermal infrared remote sensing exploits the fact that everything above absolute zero emits radiation in the thermal infrared range of the electromagnetic spectrum. These sensors record differences in the received infrared radiation from various objects. Since these differences are often considerable, an infrared image can exhibit wide range of contrasts. (*Chatterjee, 2006*) Further, for the sake of ground truth conventional borehole temperature measurement in coal seams is used to identify subsurface fires so as to validate the processed remote sensing data.

Origin of Coal Fire

Coal fires are generally ignited by mine related activities such as cutting and welding, explosives and electrical work, or transmission of surface fires to culm banks or coal seams by lightening, forest or bush fires or due to spontaneous combustion of coal. Coal reacts with atmospheric oxygen even at ambient temperatures and this reaction is exothermic. If the heat liberated during

the process is allowed to accumulate, the rate of the above reaction increases exponentially and there is a further rise in temperature. When this temperature reaches the ignition temperature of coal, the coal starts to burn and the phenomena is described as spontaneous combustion. The temperature at which the oxidation reaction in coal becomes self sustaining and spontaneous combustion occurs varies depending on the type (nature and rank) of coal and surrounding conditions of heat dissipation. In poor quality coal and where the heat retention is high the coal and carbonaceous material may start burning at temperatures as low as 30-40°C (*Kuenzer et al, 2007*).

According to US department of energy, many spontaneous fires start in storage facilities including open air stock piles, coal bunkers, and silos. The DOE attributes combustion to numerous factors. These include improperly loaded and compacted storage facilities that promote the diminution of coal into highly combustible fines and also storage for prolonged period of times, which promotes exothermic oxidation reactions in high sulfur coals. The major reasons for occurrence of coal fire due to spontaneous combustion are:

- Thick coal seam
- Plenty of coal mines in the goaf
- Presence of contiguous seams
- Coal handling procedures allowed for long-time retention of coal which increases the possibility of heating.
- New coal added on top of old coal created segregation of particle sizes, which is a major cause of heating.
- Too few temperature probes installed in the coal bunker resulted in an excessive period of time before the fire was detected.
- Failure of equipment needed to fight the fire (drag chain conveyer).
- Ineffective capability and use of carbon dioxide fire suppression system.
- Delay in the application of water.
- Inadequate policies, procedures, and training of personnel which prevent proper decision making, including the required knowledge to immediately attack the fire.
- Failure to learn lessons from past occurrences from coal bunker fires.

Surface and Subsurface fires

An open fire is defined as a coal fire that burns in direct contact with the atmosphere, usually with visible flames (Rosema et al, 1999). Open fires occur in spoil dumps of reactive coal and seams in open cast mines, but generally not at a large scale. The ground in spoil dumps is not heavily compacted and air can get through. When surface fires spread over a large area, remote sensing is a useful tool for regular monitoring and for assisting to develop management strategies.

For subsurface combustion, the requisite oxygen enters via cracks or fissures at the surface of the old abandoned mine tunnels, subsided land over the mines, etc. which are not stowed properly. There is a close relation between coal fire and subsidence which is illustrated in Fig. 1

Fig. 1: Coal Fire Subsidence Cycle (Source: Gangopadhyay and Lahiri, 2005)

Thermal Infrared Remote Sensing for Detecting of Coal Fires

All objects that have a temperature above absolute zero emit electromagnetic radiation in the range 3.0-14 μ m portion of the spectrum. Thermal Infrared remote sensing systems record thermal infrared images that can be used to determine the type of material in certain instances based on its thermal emission characteristics and evaluate if significant changes have taken place in the thermal characteristics of these phenomena over time. It is obvious that coal fires will heat the ground around them even when they are located underground, provided they are not at a great depth. (Chatterjee, 2006) This fact of ground heating provides a convenient means of detecting the coal fires using satellite or airborne remote thermal sensors. Indeed it is the only tool to survey wide areas in remote locations of Asia, particularly China, India and Indonesia, where coal fires are prevalent. The methodology in the use of remote sensing is outlined below.

The process of remote sensing can be briefly described by the following steps:

- Energy source - illuminates or provides electromagnetic energy to the target of interest.
- Radiation - energy travels from its source to the target.
- Interaction with the target - depending on the properties of both the target and the radiation.

The previous three steps apply to remote sensing making use of reflected radiation rather than detection of emitted radiation of the target. The following steps apply to both reflected and emitted radiation:

- Interaction with the atmosphere – reflected and/or radiated energy from source target is transmitted through and interacts with the atmosphere. The degree of interaction depends both on atmospheric composition along the ray path and on the height of the sensor (e.g. satellite or airborne).
- Recording of energy at the sensor - a sensor collects and records the electromagnetic radiation that has been transmitted through the atmosphere.
- Reception and processing - the data recorded by the sensor is received at a ground station where the data are processed into an image and distributed.

- Interpretation and analysis - the processed image is interpreted, visually and/or digitally, to extract information about the illuminated or emitting target.
- Application - the final element of the remote sensing process is achieved when it reveals new information or assists in solving a particular problem.

In the electromagnetic spectrum the 3-60 μ m region is referred to as the thermal infrared region. Practically, in the region with wavelengths longer than 15 μ m the energy radiation from earth's surface is insignificant and it is complicated to acquire a signal. Within the overall thermal infrared region, the 3-5 μ m and 8-14 μ m regions are used in thermal remote sensing as in the intervening part of the electromagnetic spectrum the energy is greatly absorbed by the atmospheric gases. (*Gangopadhyay and Lahiri, 2005*)

Thermal infrared sensing exploits the fact that everything above absolute zero (-273°C) emits radiation in the thermal infrared range of the electromagnetic spectrum. Thermal infrared radiation of an object is controlled mainly by several factors: the emissivity of the object, its geometry and its temperature. A perfect blackbody (an object whose temperature of emissions is controlled only by temperature) has a predictable range of wavelengths that varies as the temperature in Kelvins, and that moves to shorter wavelengths as the temperature increases (Wiens' Displacement Law). Emissivity and geometry alter this wavelength range, primarily by absorbing at wavelengths characteristic of the chemical composition of the object. The energy emitted is described by the Stefan-Boltzman Law, which relates the energy to the fourth power of the temperature. For objects with an emissivity of 1, the observed "brightness temperature" is equivalent to the kinetic temperature of the object. The conversion from brightness (remotely observed) temperature to kinetic temperature can be easily made when the characteristic emissivity of an object is known (*Knuth, 1968*). These calculations do not take into account the interactions with the atmosphere, which must be separately considered. However, when thermal contrast between objects is the intended observation, as in fire detection, atmospheric interference removal and conversion to precise kinetic temperatures is less important to the object of the exercise.

Thermal infrared sensors record the spatially averaged received infrared radiation from various objects within the target footprint. The energy recorded by a space-borne sensor is the combination of energy radiated by an object and the energy absorbed and reemitted by the atmosphere (Fig. 2). Since the differences in temperature and emissivity from one object to another are often considerable, an infrared image can exhibit a large amount of contrast. The sensors carried by aircraft or spacecraft, sensitive to this (infrared) region, provide a possible means of making synoptic measurements of land surface temperatures.

Many commercial and research satellites are now acquiring data in the thermal infrared region (8-14 μ m) all over the world. Among them Landsat7 ETM+ band 6 thermal data has 60m spatial resolution which is the highest in commercially available thermal satellites. Landsat 7 produces two thermal images, one acquired using a low gain setting (referred as band 6L) and the other using a high gain setting (referred as band 6H). Since May 2003, Landsat 7 ETM+ is semi-operational due to failure of a mechanism to properly align rows of pixels. Landsat 5 TM data,

acquired in a single band at 120m spatial resolution, can in some instances be used to provide needed data within the Landsat 7 images. Extensive work is being done to provide the best quality data possible under the circumstances. In addition, archived Landsat 5 TM data from 1984 to the at least 2007 is available. Another useful thermal scanner is aboard the multi-sensor TERRA satellite, namely ASTER. It has five channels in the thermal infrared region (8.125-8.475 μm , 8.475-8.825 μm , 8.925-9.275 μm , 10.25-10.95 μm , 10.95-11.65 μm) at 30m spatial resolution. Different methods have been developed by researchers to extract emissivity from ASTER data that can provide better surface temperature estimation in the area under consideration. Some ASTER data has also been used to compensate for Landsat 7 ETM+ errors. At a coarser resolution, AVHRR scanners with a spatial resolution of 1.1km have been aboard successive NOAA satellites since the 1980s, providing continuous data. Since 1999, thermal data from 19 different channels at 1 km resolution is available from the MODIS sensor, aboard the TERRA and AQUA satellites. All of the above satellite-based sensors are US-based. In addition, the European Space Agency has a number of thermal satellites although low-cost public access to the data is less readily available. Finally, many airborne thermal scanners exist adapted to detailed work; the Australian Daedalus scanner will be mentioned below. Since sensors and satellite systems are undergoing rapid development, the images available may change from time to time and knowledge of them needs to be updated whenever undertaking a particular project.

Coal fires on the surface, when present as flaming combustion, emit significant thermal energy that is easy to detect by any remote sensing scanner. Some of these may be at a high enough temperature to become visible in wavelength bands shorter than the thermal infrared, indeed even in the visible wavelengths. However, in the case of a subsurface coal fire the surface heating is comparatively subdued and may be masked by the solar heating or reflected solar thermal radiation during the day. In that case it is necessary to use night-time remote sensing data to reveal and measure the extent of heating.

Coal fire detection using remote sensing has three major steps:

1. Acquire a thermal image (preferably night) of the area under investigation using remote sensing and process digitally to create a surface temperature map to reveal the temperature anomalies,
2. Acquire information about local geological setting, temperatures of coal fire vents and different land covers through field survey,
3. Use geological and other field data to eliminate anomalies other than coal fires and produce a final temperature map calibrated with field collected temperatures to reveal the coal fires.

Fig. 2: Typical Diurnal Surface Temperature Variation
(Source: Gangopadhyay and Lahiri, 2005)

The process is not exactly simple, and one needs to keep several parameters in mind, particularly the atmosphere between the coal fire and the remote sensor which plays a significant role in the accuracy of the surface temperature estimation. One must also know the nature of the affected surface in terms of albedo (reflectivity), emissivity and thermal conductance. Soil moisture also affects surface temperature. A typical diurnal temperature profile is shown in Fig. above avoid surface heating due to daytime solar radiation, night-time images are needed but they are not always readily available. The table below gives the thermal properties of different surface materials.

Thermal Properties of Some Materials (CGS units for 20°C)					
Material	Thermal Conductivity	Density	Thermal Capacity	Thermal Diffusivity	Thermal Inertia
Sandstone	0.0120	2.5	0.19	0.013	0.054
Shale	0.0042	2.3	0.17	0.008	0.034
Sandy soil	0.0014	1.8	0.24	0.003	0.024
Limestone	0.0048	2.5	0.17	0.011	0.045
Coal	-	-	-	-	2.5

Conclusion

Coal fires, whether surface or subsurface, are a widespread problem in most of the coal producing countries. Thermal Infrared Remote Sensing can play a significant role in detecting and monitoring coal fires and perhaps preventing huge economic losses and environmental disasters. With pixel programming using MATLAB and proper DIP techniques, we can obtain the spatial extent with great accuracy. At present, together with conventional techniques, this technique is gaining huge importance within the researchers not only in the field of coal fire detection, but for

the monitoring of subsidence due to mine fire using Microwave Remote Sensing (SAR Interferometry).

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